

STUDY ON THE CONTROL OF MOLECULAR WEIGHT DISTRIBUTION OF THE NOVALAC OLIGOMER THROUGH PHASE SEPARATING

Qingping Feng Zaiman Huang Lingjun Wang and Yuanbin Zhou
Beijing Fiber Reinforced Plastics Research & Design Institute
Beijing, China (102101)

Summary

This report presents a method to control the molecular weight distribution of the novolac oligomer by modulating the stirrer pattern during the synthesis process. Because the molecular weight distribution of the novolac oligomer is directly related to the melt viscosity and the cured structure, it has great influence on the process and performance of the novolac resin in many cases. How to control the molecular weight and its contribution of the widely used novolac resin attracts much more attentions in the field of phenolic resin production. The synthesis reaction mechanism of the novolac is commonly known as condensation polymerization. It is difficult to control the molecular distribution of the novolac resin in a narrow scope, especially when the molecules are in such a size of several phenol rings. In this paper, a model was set up to simulate the phase separating in the course of the novolac reaction, according to the model, the process is greatly improved. Consequently, the novolac resin of perfectly distributing molecular weight was prepared, its mainly concluded trimer and tetramer.

Key words: novolac oligomer, molecular weight distribution, phase separation

INTRODUCTION

Phenolic polymers are char-forming polymeric materials, the particular combination of thermochemical and thermophysical properties of these char-forming polymers have made them of special interest as high-temperature-resistant, flame-retardant polymeric materials^[1].

Phenolic polymers as one of the oldest commercially produced plastics known, was developed and featured in the early 1900s^[2]. Phenolic resins thus became the first truly synthetic polymers to be developed. Because of the complexity and number of end products produced in the phenolic reaction, there was great difficulty in identifying and showing the structure of the product formed, people haven't stopped to research and apply them since then, though many new phenolic derived polymers have been prepared, the novolac oligomer still has its fascination for its perfect char structure, longer storage time and larger elongation. Generally, the novolac oligomer is cured by hexamethylenetetramine under 120~200°C. However, as an ablative resist resin, the char yield and the structure are basically relied on the oligomer's chemical structure, the ideal molecular structures are those including trimer, tetramer and pentamer, the influence of the molecular weight distribution on the char yield is different from the popular knowledge, which had been indicated by another paper^[3].

The novolac oligomer is prepared by phenol and formaldehyde under acid catalyzer, such as oxalic acid, sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acid, the oxalic acid is usually used for its moderate catalyst effect. Because the phenol has three active positions, it is necessary that the ratio of phenol to formaldehyde must be less than 1, or else, the oligomer will be crosslinked during the production. The reaction described as below^[4]

If the novolac resin has not properly molecular weight distribution, the behaviors of final composite products are poor in all probability. The average molecular weight can be controlled through several methods according to its application and the plant condition, for example, lowering the ratio of formaldehyde and phenol and prolonging the reaction to raise the reactive degree, the molecular weight can be reduced, its molecular weight distribution may be controlled to some extent. In this paper, study result shows that the molecular weight distribution of novolac oligomer is difficult to be controlled during the polymerization by ordinary methods, such as changing the ratios of raw materials or reaction temperature. In fact, it can be commanded conveniently by making use of the phase separation phenomena during the process of the condensation polymerization.

EXPERIMENT

Materials

Phenol: the main raw material phenol used in all the cases was produced by Yanshan petrochemical company, China

Formaldehyde: the other main raw material – formaldehyde was produced by Beijing chemical plant, China

Oxalic acid: the catalyst, obtained commercially from the chemical reagent shop

Test Procedures and Methods

Synthesis process: raw materials, including phenol, formaldehyde and Oxalic acid, which molar ratios are approach to 1: 0.89: 0.01, are fed into a three-neck flask equipped with condensator and electric stirrer, react under 85~95℃ for 0.5~1.5 hours, the feeds became turbid for phase-seperating, go on react for 3~5 hours, then the Oxalic acid was washed-out by water. Finally, the primitive oligomer was unwatered by vacuum pump.

The measure of molecular weight distribution: the molecular weight distribution is measured by field-desorption (FD)mass spectrometry, which is a soft ionization technique developed by Karas and Hillenkamp and is now an established technique for the analysis of synthetic polymers, can provide absolute molecular masses for each oligomeric species^[5]. the method is much more direct than other traditional method, such as viscosity and other method based on the physical specialities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The facts influencing the molecular weight distribution of novolac oligomer

During the process of the novolac oligomer reaction, the phenol and formaldehyde can be treated as difunctional monomers, and the reaction mechanism is similar to the step growth polymerization. As a linear condensation polymer, the degree of polymerization can be calculated as below:

$$\overline{X_n} = \frac{1 + r}{1 + r - 2rp}$$

Where $\overline{X_n}$: degree of polymerization

R: the ratio of the raw material

P: degree of reaction

the molecular weight distribution of condensation polymer can be shown as below:

$$\frac{\overline{X_w}}{\overline{X_n}} = 1 + p$$

where $\overline{X_w}$: the number average molecular weight

$\overline{X_n}$: the weight average molecular weight

p : the degree of the reaction

Typically, because the reaction of preparing novolac oligomer is linear condensation polymer, the molecular weight and its distribution should obey the same rule of the linear condensation polymerization, according to this rule, the $\overline{X_n}$ of novolac oligomer can be controlled into pentamer, but the molecular weight distribution is much broader compared with the ordinary linear condensation, the reasons mainly based on the following facts.

Firstly, the reaction is much more complete in contrast to the ordinary linear condensation polymer because the phenol has three functional groups. the three active positions may led the novolac oligomer to be branched or cross-linked during the reaction under certain conditions, such as higher acid concentration and higher ratio of phenol to formaldehyde. According to the Carothers equation that describes the multi- groups condensation polymerization, the ratio of the formaldehyde to phenol better not to be more than 0.9, or else the reaction may run a risk to bring about cross-linking, which causes the viscosity of the oligomer to raise highly and seriously influences on the later process of novolac oligomer composite. While the ratio should neither be less than 0.8, as the reaction continue, the concentrations of the reactants are lowered and the reactive speed reduces a lot, the reaction is under equilibrium, the free phenol will go beyond the application limit to damage the properties of the novolac oligomer.

Secondly, there are three active different reaction position in phenol structure. According to Richard' research about the reaction of phenol and formaldehyde under acid catalyst, the para-para methane existed first, after 0.5hour, ortho- para methane existed, finally, after 1.5 hours the ortho-ortho methane exists^[6]. From the result we could conclude that the para position was more active than two ortho positions. For this reason, once the para-para dimer is formed, the chance to increase is less than the ortho-ortho dimer or the ortho- para dimer, even less than the oligomer having more than three phenol rings. As a result, in a system which the groups and catalyzer are evenly distributed, some molecules may increase to more big ones while major of the monomers only transform into dimmers.

By traditional methods, such as changing the reaction temperature or reaction time, we only obtained novolac oligomer with broader molecular weight distribution. The typical molecular weight distribution is showed as figure 1. the experience results are showed in table 1

Table 1 the traditionally controlling the molecular weight distribution

NO.	Reaction temperature(°C)	Reaction time(hours)	FD-MS characterization	NMR characterization
1	86-90	3	Dimer and big molecular	478
2	86-90	5	Dimer and big molecular	605
3	90-95	3	Dimer and big molecular	611
4	90-95	5	Dimer and big molecular	697

Note : all the tests are carried out under strongly stirring

From the table, the results indicate that through general controlling methods, we can only obtained novolac oligomer mainly composed of dimer and big molecules because of the reactive complication.

Figure 1 the worse distribution the molecular weight

Model for control molecular weight distribution

For it falls to failure in controlling the molecular weight distribution of novolac oligomer by general methods, a model is set up to simulate the reaction process, which indicates the microstructure of the reactant system, after making use of the phase-separating phenomena during the reaction, a new controlling method is then found to control the molecular weight distribution. The model is showed as figure 2

Figure 2 The model of the phase separation in the process of the novolac oligomer

The model shows : as the reaction begins, some molecules react to larger molecular weight, phenol and formaldehyde continue to be monomer state, when the concentration of the larger molecules reaches to some degree, the solvency reduces and macro-phase-separation comes to exist, at the turbid point, only small part of tetramer, pentamer and hexamer are synthesized, the figure 3 has showed the molecular weight distribution. As the reaction continue, the monomers react further, and the concentration of the polymer increases further until the reactive system reach to equilibrium, the concrete process is described as below:

1. At the beginning of the reaction, the various ingredients of raw materials are mixed into one compatible phase
2. as the reaction continue, the tetramer, pentamer and hexamer are solved in the monomer solvent, before the turbid point, the system is still one compatible phase.
3. as the concentration of the tetramer, pentamer and hexamer rise to some degree, the system becomes phase-separating, a resin phase and a water phase are formed, the density of the water phase is lower than the density of the resin phase. Further more, because the catalyst has a better solubility in the water phase than in the organic phase, the reaction mainly continues in the water phase and the interface between the water phase and the resin phase.
4. As the reaction goes on, the monomers in the water phase reduce further and the oligomers with certain molecular weight get into the resin (organic) phase continually until the equilibrium come to exist.

Figure 3 the molecular weight distribution on the turbid point

The speed of stirring and type of the stirrer play an important role in the process of phase separating during the reaction. According to the model, the stirring can be changed by two methods, the first method is only to reduce the speed after the turbid point. As the reaction goes on, the oligomers with certain molecular weight get into the resin (organic) phase continually. If the stirring speed is lowered enough, the oligomer will have a better distribution for some uses (Fig.2). But if the stirring is strong enough, the resin phase will be highly dispersed, the raw materials can react with the oligomer in the large interphases. The second method is to rise the position of the stirrer, let the stirrer work in the water phase and the speed of the stirrer is keeping the same speed. Then the resulted novolac oligomer gradually separate from this water soluble phase to an organic phase and stop polymerizing, while the rest of the raw materials including the catalyzer are still remain in the water phase to continue the reaction.

The experiment result

Under the guide of the model, a variety of novolac oligomers are synthesized. Though the reactive temperature and the reactive time are different, the distributions of the molecular weight are controlled to ideal result through both reducing stirrer speed and rising the stirrer position. The all oligomer contain mainly trimer, tethamer and pentamer, while the dimmer concentration is much lower than those that are synthesized under general condition. The experience results are showed in table 2 and figure 4.

Table 2 the newly controlling molecular weight distribution

No	Reaction temperature(°C)	Stirrer pattern	FD-MS characterization
1	85-90	Reduce speed	Main in tethamer
2	90-95	Reduce speed	Main in tethamer
3	85-90	Rise position	Main in tethamer
4	90-95	Rise position	Main in tethamer

Figure 4 the distribution of molecular weight after changing the speed pattern

For the methods of controlling distribution of molecular weight result in making use of the phase separating, it simplifies the controlling process and neglects the complexion of the oligomer kinetics. The method of controlling molecular weight distribution can be used in many other reaction in which there is a phase separate phenomena.

CONCLUSION

Novolac oligomer acts as a favorable ablative resistant materials and flame retardant materials, controlling the distribution of molecular weight is important, it is our chief goal to let the melt viscosity to be low enough to process conveniently and the structure of the cured resin to be perfect. The paper presents a method , which makes fully use of the phase separating during the reaction, changes the stirrer pattern, so that the novolac oligomer can be controlled into including mainly trimer, tetramer and pentamer, the bigger molecular and the free phenol and dimmer are lowered not to influence the processing and property.

ACKNOWLEDGE

The authors would like to thank professor Hongzhan Xiao for measure the distribution of molecular weight.

REFERENCES

1. YZAKS, JELEN LO, D.RAUCHER. Some Structure-Property Relationships in Polymer Flammability: Studies of Phenolic-Derived Polymers. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 27, 913-930 (1982)
2. T.H.DAILEY, D.LYONS. Phenolic Reinforced Plastics in America- A Status Update. 45th Annual Conference, Composites Institute, The Society of the Plastics Industry, Inc. February 12-15, 1990, session 13-B
3. Zhongmin Xue , The Influence of the Molecular Weight Distribution of Novolac Oligomer on the Char Residue of the Cured Phenolic Formaldehyde Resin
4. N.J.L.MEGSON. Phenolic Resin Chemistry. Butterworths Scientific Publications, 1958
5. Humayun Mandal and Allan S.Hay. M.A.L.D.I.-T.O.F. Mass Spectrometry Characterization of 4-Alkyl Substituted Phenol-Formaldehyde Novolac Type Resins. *Polymer* vol.38 No.26. pp6267-6271
6. Richard A, Pethrick and Barry Thomson, ¹³C Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Studies of Phenol-Formaldehyde. Resins and Related Model Compounds, 2-Analysis of Sequence Structure in Resins. *British Polymer Journal*, 1986, 18(6):380-386